

Breaking Down Boundaries Between Different Engineering Disciplines – My Experiences of Collaborating with Prof. Nina Thornhill

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Abstract: Between 2010 and 2020 Prof. Nina Thornhill closely collaborated with ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków, Poland. Since 2012, the author has worked directly with Nina in a number of large projects and has hosted Nina and members of her research group on extended placements at the center in Kraków on multiple occasions. Together, along with co-collaborators, they have worked on advanced data analytics methods which aim to transcend the traditional boundaries between different engineering disciplines, for example considering the interaction between industrial processes and the transmission grid. During the period of common work, the author has learned a great deal from Prof. Thornhill. In this article, the author provides a summary of his experiences of working with Nina during this period.

Keywords: Include a list of 5-10 keywords, preferably taken from the IFAC keyword list.

1. INTRODUCTION

I was first introduced to Professor Nina Thornhill in January 2012 when I assumed responsibilities for managing ABB Corporate Research Center in Krakow's involvement in third party funded activities. At this time our center was already engaged in the REAL-SMART and ENERGY-SMARTOPS projects, both of which were being coordinated by Nina. Since this time, Nina and colleagues at the center have worked closely together on a practically daily basis, both in the scope of these projects, in the scope of subsequent similar projects and in the scope of Nina's role as ABB Chair of Process Automation at Imperial College. This collaboration has been hugely beneficial to colleagues at the research center, both on a professional and a personal level. In this short article I intend to provide a short synopsis of Nina's technical work with ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków. This work has primarily focussed on algorithms and methods, which combine advanced data analytics methods with multidisciplinary domain expertise in order to create solutions which transcend the traditional boundaries between different engineering disciplines. In the article I also wish to highlight what I believe to be Nina's key character traits which have resulted in her achieving great academic and industry success. As is the case for the numerous researchers who have also worked with Nina, these traits have directly influenced my own personal development and future outlook. Furthermore, I am sure that they will ensure that Nina will have a fulfilling, enjoyable and well-deserved retirement.

2. THE REAL-SMART PROJECT, 2010-2014

My first interactions with Nina came in the scope of the Marie Curie Industry-Academic Pathways and Partnership (IAPP) Project "Real-Smart." This project focussed on the use of real-time measurements for monitoring and management of power transmission dynamics in Smart Grid

applications. The project promoted collaboration between a network of interdisciplinary experts, primarily through secondments between different industrial and academic partners. In this project, ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków had the pleasure of hosting two PhD Researchers who were supervised by Nina at Imperial College, Inês Cecílio and Izzati Mohd Noor. We were also lucky enough to host Nina herself.

Our first significant collaboration came when we hosted Inês Cecílio in the second quarter of 2012. Inês worked with a compressor experimental system located at the center, investigating how electrical disturbances propagate from the electrical subsystems into connected mechanical elements and subsequently into the process. Whilst the initial secondment was a resounding success, it became clear that continued collaboration would be beneficial to all. With the full support of Nina, Inês returned to Kraków the following year to work with colleagues at the center further. The forecasted additional results were realized beyond expectations with the work supporting the publication of articles relating to multivariate approaches for detecting disturbances and disturbance propagations in systems irrespective of whether the various signals considered in the analysis are sampled at different rates [1-5]. The differing dynamics of electrical, mechanical and process subsystems mean that the signals used for control and monitoring of each tend to be sampled at different rates. The research conducted in the scope of this collaboration represented an attempt to better understand and leverage the interactions between the different subsystems in a plant, in essence bridging the interfaces between different engineering domains. This research direction would continue to be present in our subsequent collaborations with Nina.

During 2012 and 2013 Prof. Thornhill spent three separate periods on secondment at ABB Corporate Research Center in

Kraków in the scope of the Real-Smart Project. The first period of Prof. Thornhill's stay at the center took place between 22nd July until 28th September 2012. The second period of Prof. Thornhill's stay took place between 18th March until 17th April 2013. Prof. Thornhill's third stay took place between 15th July until 6th September 2013. During these three secondments, Nina developed a roadmap for future research related to Industrial Smart Grids. Again this research looked to bridge the interfaces between different engineering domains. In this instance Nina investigated the opportunities for ensuring smooth operation of a transmission system by allowing large industrial loads to vary their consumption in a flexible, yet controlled manner. Clearly already an expert in the operation of industrial process systems, during the secondment Nina showed her penchant for continuous learning, applying herself in the study of the basics of power systems engineering, supported by experts at the center. These collaborations helped broaden the knowledge and understanding of the different engineering domains of all involved, allowing opportunities in interdisciplinary topics to be uncovered.

From March to June 2014, Izzati Mohd Noor was hosted at ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków. Izzati was the second Imperial College PhD Researcher supervised by Nina to visit the center in the scope of the RealSmart project. Building on the work of Nina and others in the project, Izzati's work focused on detailing the effects of variable operation of industrial plant on the electrical grid. Specifically Izzati worked on developing numerical simulation models of a grid, which could subsequently be linked to a model of a process system (specifically a compressor system). After completing the secondment, Izzati and Nina continued to develop the methods, with both subsequently returning to Kraków to discuss findings and plan associated publications. As with the other previous placements, this work further illustrated the opportunities and challenges present when developing solutions which span multiple disciplines. Furthermore, if Ines' work addressed this problem using data-driven modelling and signal processing approaches, and Nina attacked this problem via a comprehensive review of available academic and industrial literature, Izzati's work was based upon a detailed mathematical modelling approach. Given that all of these research directions were guided by Prof. Thornhill, it is clear that she is willing to tackle a research problem using a number of different methods, and is not wedded to a single favoured approach. As a result, Nina is skilled in a vast array of different approaches. This further increases the ease of collaboration between Nina and colleagues from various different technical backgrounds.

The Real-Smart project was the first such project funded by the European Commission which I was involved in. It was expertly coordinated by Nina and the team at Imperial College. The project initiated various collaborations both between ABB and Imperial College, as well as with other partners, strengthened through engaging network meetings which took place at various wonderful locations across Europe. The results delivered in this project are becoming ever more relevant, particularly as recent advances in

digitalization are also serving to break down the traditional barriers between different engineering disciplines.

3. THE ENERGY SMART-OPS PROJECT, 2011-2015

From 2011 to 2015 Nina and Imperial College coordinated a second project which brought together expertise from multiple disciplines in order to create innovative and industrially relevant solutions. The "Energy savings from smart operation of electrical, process and mechanical equipment" project, otherwise known as "Energy-SmartOps," was a Marie Curie Actions Networks for Initial Training (ITN) project which funded the doctoral training of 15 Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) based at a number of academic and industrial partners, including ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków. This project further demonstrated to me how Nina is willing to go above and beyond in order to support her colleagues. In particular, she was always available to talk to Early-Stage Researchers, providing opportunity to discuss technical or organizational challenges being faced. At the same time, her open and friendly nature, meant that researchers felt happy to approach her. In particular, I remember the fun and creative discussions had between Nina, myself and the three Early Stage Researchers (Victor Jaramillo, Gregorio Ferreira and Alejandro Fernandez) based in Kraków during Nina's 2012-2013 secondment at the center.

The Energy SmartOps project itself delivered a number of advanced algorithms relating to: (i) Fusing Condition Monitoring Information from Multiple Systems to Improve Root Cause Analysis and reduce false alarms; (ii) Advanced scheduling solutions for saving energy; (iii) Specific maintenance and control solutions for rotating machinery. Similar to the Real-Smart project, Energy SmartOps promoted the idea that new technologies can grow by considering systems holistically, ignoring separations between different engineering domains. Again, guided by Nina's expert coordination, the project was a great success, both in terms of developing new technology and, perhaps more valuably, in providing training that allows the already extremely talented ESRs to be successful in their future lives. Since this project, all have gone on to greater achievements. This is very fulfilling to those who participated in the project, and is also something for which Nina herself should be very proud.

4. THE PRONTO PROJECT, 2014-2020 AND NINA'S SABBATICAL AT ABB CORPORATE RESEARCH IN KRAKÓW, 2017-2019

As the Energy SmartOps project approached its conclusion in 2014, it became apparent that there was considerable scope for a follow-up project building on the developments and collaborations already in place. Given her outstanding record in both creating interesting and comprehensive project proposals that attract funding, and in successfully leading the execution of the resulting projects, there was little resistance when Nina was proposed to act as project coordinator of a new project. After considerable efforts on the part of Nina in coordinating both the technical content of the proposal and

the organizational aspects such as agreeing secondments between partners, the PRONTO (PROcess NeTwork Optimization) project was submitted in January 2015 and was granted funding by the European Commission in the following May. The project is a European Industrial Doctorate program funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions scheme under EU Horizon 2020. Like the Energy SmartOps project, PRONTO offers 13 Early Stage Researchers training structured in the form of industrially relevant Ph.D. projects. Notably, the projects include long-term placements between partners, with each researcher being required to spend at least 18 months working with an industrial partner.

Whilst the original project proposal was written in late 2014 and early 2015, the technical topics addressed by the PRONTO project have been found to be increasingly relevant particularly as digital technologies become ever more important. Researchers working in the project investigate new data analytics methods to extract information from large, heterogeneous assemblies of data in order to determine machinery condition and process performance in a more reliable, robust and comprehensive manner. The project also investigates how to make best use of this information, through the development of methods for optimizing operations, materials, energy and wastes taking machinery condition and process performance into account. Again the project looks to develop advanced analytics and optimization approaches that combine expertise (and data) from a number of different engineering domains to achieve tangible improvements.

The PRONTO project includes long-term placements between partners, with each Early Stage Researcher being required to spend at least 18 months working with an industrial partner. As a result, I have had the privilege to be industrial supervisor of three excellent PhD Students, all of whom were hosted at ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków for considerable periods of time during the period 2016-2019. Very luckily, this period has coincided with Nina spending over 2 years on sabbatical leave at our center. Whilst this has clearly been beneficial for our PRONTO Early Stage Researchers based in Kraków, I see that Nina's stay at the center has helped me develop my approaches to supervising researchers.

Since July 2017 we have had the enormous honour of hosting Nina at ABB Corporate Research Center. Originally planned to take place between July 2017 until September 2018, we were also very happy to agree to extend Nina's stay for a further year. As of writing, Nina is in the final months of her sabbatical stay in Kraków. As with the previous placements and secondments which Nina has been in some way involved, the experience has been extremely productive and enjoyable for all.

During her extended time in Kraków, Nina has looked to further strengthen her links with industry, further consolidating and disseminating her previous research work at the interface between processes and connected systems, through discussions with relevant product and technology managers. A second activity which Nina, Trond Haugen

(ABB Norway) and I have been working on during Nina's sabbatical relates to understanding how Nina's previous work relates to Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Autonomous Systems, three fields which are gaining ever greater visibility in society. The work has confirmed that Nina's previous work continues to be extremely relevant, both today and into the future. As digital technologies such as the Internet of Things make systems and people ever more connected, the algorithms and methods developed by Nina at the interfaces between different systems have great value. Nina presented some of the thoughts and findings arising from this activity, as well as some selected results, during her lecture accompanying her receipt of the Nordic Process Control Award at the 22nd Nordic Process Control Workshop at the Technical University of Denmark. Nina concluded this lecture with some observations for the future researchers of younger generations. As well as her excellent technical record, it is her ever-present willingness to support younger researchers which is extremely inspiring.

In addition to these specific tasks, during her sabbatical in Kraków, Nina has continued to coordinate the PRONTO project. During her stay, one of the academic project partners decided to leave the project consortium. This had implications for Ruomu Tan, an early stage researcher who was originally enrolled on a PhD at the leaving partner, and at the time was engaged on her 18 month industrial placement at ABB Corporate Research in Kraków. Nina mitigated the change superbly, minimizing any disruption and agreeing to take over the academic supervision of Ruomu's PhD studies, with Ruomu transferring to Imperial College. During the sabbatical Nina participated in regular status update meetings with the three Early Stage Researchers hosted at the center, Ruomu, Anna Stief and Tian Cong. In addition, Nina has continued to supervise her other students based at other locations, with many of them also visiting our center.

The technical results of these collaborations, guided by Nina, have been numerous and outstanding. Collaborations between Nina, early stage researchers, project partners and colleagues at our center have generated a benchmark dataset for developing and testing analytics methods for heterogeneous data [6]; new methods for selecting and fusing discrete and continuous process measurements for fault detection [7-8]; a new kernel for Kernel-PCA methods which allows faults to be better distinguished in nonlinear systems with multiple operating modes [9]; and a complete analytics workflow, which combines this novel Kernel with clustering techniques to detect anomalies in process systems and, if the anomaly is proven to be a healthy operating mode, easily perform model retraining to incorporate this new information [10]. A number of other technical contributions, ranging from comprehensive review articles in industrially relevant and pressing topics, through to highly theoretical papers which indicate new best practices for process monitoring are currently being worked on. In every document that a researcher submits for review, Nina provides outstanding feedback. Every comment is supplemented with detailed information regarding the fundamental reasoning for her comment, be it explaining grammatical rules, through to insightful technical

background. As a result, every paper that Nina works on is of high standard, and students go away from the writing process better equipped to formulate their ideas logically, to argue their views and to investigate potentially fruitful research directions.

Having started in July 2017, Prof. Thornhill's sabbatical at ABB Corporate Research Center in Kraków is due to conclude in November 2019. The PRONTO project is due to conclude one month later. This will mark approximately 10 years of direct collaboration between the ABB center in Kraków and Nina. The collaboration has resulted in a large number of technical advances in topics associated with data analytics, particularly at the interfaces between industrial processes and connected mechanical and electrical systems – topics which are gaining ever more importance as digitalization pervades industry. The collaboration has provided a number of highly skilled researchers the tools and guidance which will surely set them on the path to great careers. And finally the collaboration has nurtured great and lasting friendships between Nina and a number of colleagues at the center.

5. EXPERIENCES OF WORKING WITH PROF. NINA THORNHILL

In this section I would like to briefly summarize some of my personal experiences of working with Prof. Nina Thornhill over the past 7 years.

When I think of Nina, a first thought which comes to my mind is supportive. Despite her considerable success in academic and industrial contexts, Nina is one of the most approachable people you may find, whoever you may be. She is very friendly and is great company. Furthermore, she goes out of her way to help anyone who needs it.

Nina leads by example. The technical quality of her work is extremely high and she has a natural intuition over what questions need to be asked. Whilst she is quite adept at finding the thread which causes a particular technical concept to unravel, she is also talented at proposing the solutions to any challenges uncovered. The resulting work is much more robust, reliable and retains relevance for a number of years.

Nina performs every task diligently. Her conscientious approach has helped bring structure to large complex projects, such as Real-Smart, Energy SmartOps and PRONTO. From a personal development viewpoint, I particularly feel Nina has influenced my approaches to supervision of researchers. For example, Nina's approach to providing feedback goes above and beyond, and I aspire to be as good a supervisor as she is.

Nina is always willing to learn and develop herself. She is willing to admit if she does not know the answer to a question and strives to find solutions. During her first placement at our center in Krakow, Nina spent time studying the field of power systems engineering, discussing with experts at the center. During her sabbatical, Nina also started learning Polish, leveraging her study of Latin at school to understand the grammar 'rules' of the language.

These character traits have directly influenced my own personal development and future outlook. Furthermore, I am sure that they will ensure that Nina and her husband will have a fulfilling, enjoyable and well-deserved retirement.

It has been a pleasure and a privilege to work closely with Nina over the past seven years. We all look forward to continuing our collaboration as friends as she moves into her next projects in retirement.

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